

Modeling Interactions between Autonomous Agents in a Multi-Agent Self-Awareness Architecture

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Abstract—Learning from experience is a fundamental capability of intelligent agents. Autonomous systems rely on sensors that provide data about the environment and internal situations to their perception systems for learning and inference mechanisms. These systems can also learn Self-Aware and Situation-Aware generative modules from these data to localize themselves and interact with the environment. In this paper, we propose a self-aware cognitive architecture capable to perform tasks where the interactions between the self-state of an agent and the surrounding environment are explicitly and dynamically represented. We specifically develop a Deep Learning (DL) based Self-Aware interaction model, empowered by learning from Multi-Modal Perception (MMP) and World Models using multi-sensory data in a novel Multi-Agent Self-Awareness Architecture (MASAA). Two sub-modules are developed, the Situation Model (SM) and the First-Person model (FPM), that address different and interrelated aspects of the World Model (WM). The MMP model, instead, aims at learning the mapping of different sensory perceptions into Exteroceptive (EI) and Proprioceptive (PI) latent information. The WM then uses the learned MMP model as experience to predict dynamic self-behaviors and interaction patterns within the experienced environment. WM and MMP Models are learned in a data-driven way, starting from the lower-dimensional odometry data used to guide the learning of higher-dimensional video data, thus generating coupled Generalized State Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks (GS-HDBNs). We test our model on KITTI, CARLA, and iCab datasets, achieving high performance and a low average localization error (RMSE) of 2.897%, when considering two interacting agents.

Index Terms—Multi-Modal Perception, World Model, Variational Autoencoder, Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks, Linear Prediction Models

I. INTRODUCTION

SELF AWARE interaction modeling is an essential component of autonomous driving. To be self-aware, an agent should be capable of jointly handling

knowledge related to sensing, perceiving, interpreting, planning, and acting in an efficient framework. To this end, this paper aims to build an interaction model for autonomous agents that enables them to understand their own state and interact with the surrounding environment. Uncertainty connected to the interaction components, like observations and hidden state variables and their relations, makes it necessary to choose an appropriate representation. Probability theory offers a coherent natural basis to this end. Probabilistic interaction models [1], [2], [3] can be used to model cross inter-dependencies of the interacting sub-systems and predict deviations from expected dynamic behaviors. Such models handle variables that can represent the environment, and incorporate prior beliefs about its state as well as the model of the agent's state. Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBNs) [4], [5] are Probabilistic Graphical Models (PGMs) that have been proved to embed the features described above. They are efficient generative tools that represent uncertain causal relationships between variables, allowing the use of inference mechanisms for the estimation and self-organizing incremental learning of new models within homeostatic processes [6]. In general, these capabilities are the core characteristics of self-awareness models.

DBNs are well suited for jointly modeling, in a coherent way, discrete and continuous variables coming from multi-sensorial data and representing model components at different abstraction levels hierarchically. As discussed in [7], Hierarchical DBNs (H-DBNs) can robustly represent fusion models, considering heterogeneous time-series multi-sensorial signals within artificial agents. The fusion process can be represented as a generative model, by integrating perception and action tasks using hidden states related to the agent and the external world (environment) [8].

Perceiving, representing, and acting in a dynamic environment results from interconnected and incremental processes, which can be learned using a probabilistic inference methodology. These learned models aim to estimate the environment's general state jointly with the agent's self-state, as a self-aware agent. Therefore, self-awareness is based on representing the ego agent and possible interacting agents that share the same environment. Self-awareness maps sensory observations in a mental space (here defined as the World Model), where dynamic behaviors and intentions of objects are represented at different resolution levels [9]. Being able to autonomously navigate an environment is an example of a process that can benefit from self-awareness. This type of navigation has been carried out by following heuristic and optimal approaches [10].

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This paper has supplementary downloadable material available at <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>, provided by the authors. The material provides a detailed explanation of the components within the MASAA architecture, including a thorough description of the input/output decomposition for each component. Supporting results and simplified architectural diagrams are also provided. This material is 1.68 MB in size.

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In the heuristic approaches, autonomy is reached by applying empirical rules governing the model behavior. Such rules form a model that can achieve an immediate goal by driving the agent to focus on parts of the sensed environment relevant to the task. Heuristic methods are task-specific and mostly face substantial limitations, especially in complex environments. Maze-solving vehicles [11], and robotic vacuum cleaner agents [12] are examples using this approach. Now, let us consider a dynamic cognitive context where the agent uses self-awareness to model world state and perception modalities (e.g., attention focusing, perception, and filtering) concurrently. In this case, a global optimization problem has to be defined.

Optimal coupling between sensed data and World Model variables has to be driven by the optimization of an objective function that depends on the future states of the vehicle, including those that can be determined by planning and action taking. In this approach, the agent updates a model of the environment at each observation step (starting from an initial one), and it figures out an optimal path to reach the destination using heuristic rules. In this way, despite coupling between attention focusing on sensory data, the World Model states can be optimized. Often, the selected World Model contains heuristic rules, in order to determine agent intentions, that do not allow the system to couple dynamics in attention-focusing with agent action policies in an explainable way. Such methods used in autonomous navigation, such as in ORB-SLAM [13], [14], give good results using the Bag of Words method [15] for loop closure detection and relative pose estimation. Also, global bundle adjustment is used to improve the accuracy further. Moreover, feature-based [16], [17] and stereo-matching-based [18] methods are state-of-the-art methods performing well, but they do not consider ego-action and environment modeling coherently (together), as map creation is separate from action. These different SLAM methods simultaneously build localization and global mapping for an agent. Here, instead, we are developing a latent state local trajectory, stored in the MMP model, as an ordered hallucinated (inside-out [19]) collection of high-dimensional stimuli. These are coming from Generalized State Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks (GS-HDBNs) [20] that an agent will learn internally, from low-dimensional World Models, as a local latent representation and inference of a map trajectory.

In general, autonomous navigation is not easy, as environments can change and not be perfectly known [21]. In order to create a plan, the agent needs to build a continuously updated model of the regularly changing environment. The more uncertainty in the environment and the environment model, the harder it is to create stable maps, i.e., map models that allow one to localize oneself at each fraction of a second. Hence an autonomous vehicle must reach its destination efficiently, while following local traffic laws and avoiding other cars driven by different types of drivers in rainy, snowy, and other challenging conditions.

Our work is motivated by Lecun’s general AI [22] and Seth’s general controlled hallucination theory [19]. We propose a coupled Perception and World Model representation and inference framework, learned from data, by introducing a new cognitive self-awareness architecture. The perception

model is learned from higher-dimensional data, through a self-supervised approach that uses a World Model obtained from low-dimensional sensors. In this way, higher dimensional data are explored in a controlled hallucination modality, where control is experienced by unsupervised low-dimensional models. We follow the optimization approach, through the optimization of a complex objective function designed to have no heuristic rules for the World Model stage. In other words, the agent learns World Models by observing a series of latent space data produced by lower-dimensional sensors, and perception models from higher-dimensional sensors guided by the World Models themselves. Such models, in turn, can be improved incrementally when the agent interacts with new environmental setups based on anomaly signals.

This paper introduces a general cognitive architecture, Multi-Agent Self-Awareness Architecture (MASAA), for autonomous systems (Fig. 1). The architecture has the following characteristics: adaptability to self-awareness learning frameworks, scalability to represent multi-ego agents, reliability in representing and doing inference of heterogeneous agents, conceptual integrity in representing an overall vision of reasoning, and maintainability of its components. In the current implementation stage, the Active First Person Model (AFPM) and the instructions associated with the action model are not considered. We focused on developing the Multi-Modal Perception (MMP) and the World Model (WM) models, communicating through the Short-Term Memory Module. At the inference stage, the Cost Module measures the deviation of learned models from the current environmental setups (observations), indicating whether to adapt or use the model as it is. WM and MMP can jointly represent the dynamic evolution of knowledge sets where an agent can project its states and interact with the neighboring agents. These models are designed and implemented to achieve autonomous self-localization and overtaking interaction tasks. In particular, we consider self-aware overtaking interaction tasks of two interacting agents by building a hierarchy of knowledge from multi-sensorial signals in a Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks (HDBNs) framework. The major contributions of our work are:

- We propose an overall novel cognitive architecture with all modules learning hierarchy of representations for hierarchical prediction and resolutions under uncertainty.
- We analyze Bayesian generative and predictive models, evaluating the effectiveness of MMP and WM, for a generalizable interaction modeling demonstrated through overtaking maneuver. Overtaking is selected as a particular type of maneuvering to show the performance of our MASAA framework.
- We build the best dynamic coupling between *experience modeling* from higher dimensional sensor information, and *attention focusing* from lower dimensional sensor information, to minimize the prediction error while doing joint tasks (self-localization and interaction).

II. RELATED WORKS

This section reviews some studies on self-awareness architectures and self-localization for interacting autonomous

Fig. 1: MASAA: Cognitive architecture for autonomous agents. Arrows 1 to 5 are processes, based on model output errors, for correcting (changing) the corresponding model as an incremental learning process. The sensing module is a hardware module interfacing with the external world by translating physical stimuli into an initial internal representation. It produces a time series of different observations for both the WM and MMP modules. The WM processes the incoming lower dimensional data and produces vocabularies representing the agent’s self-state in a context. The MMP module uses the WM vocabulary as a guiding attentive knowledge. The integrated WM representation is used as an encoded collection memory of sensorial active experiences of the agent, to be used when the agent has to perform experienced tasks. The learned WM Situation model is applied under a First-Person viewpoint as a result of embedded explicit relations between external and internal variables. The short-term memory module represents the communication module, which is the interaction medium using Markov Jump Particle Filtering. The Active First-Person module is an online process that selects actions based on learned policies and transfers action commands to the Actuation module.

agents.

A. Self-awareness System Architectures

A software architecture defines the characteristics of a system and its interconnected components that work together to accomplish a particular objective. Considering self-awareness model software architectures, the architecture discussed in [23] can be used as a base reference architecture. It describes a conceptual framework for self-aware and self-expressive capabilities. The study [23] illustrates different components of self-awareness (Stimulus Awareness, Interaction Awareness, Time Awareness, Goal Awareness, Meta-Self-Awareness, and Collective and Emergent Self-Awareness) that can be considered as a foundation for self-awareness architectures. Even if the paper describes and shows different design methods, it does not give explicit implementation details. In addition, in that study, the incremental online learning model and the associated cost modules are not tackled properly, which are essential components of an artificial self-aware agent. These components are

instead explicitly incorporated into our architecture. In [24], a task-based architecture is presented, with three categories, i.e., sensing, perception, and decision-making. The architecture is very compact and does not clearly specify how components communicate in the application layer. The model integration and how each model is updated through the self-awareness incremental learning and decision-making components are missing. In our work, these modules are integrated and learned in a unified manner to enable the agent to self-correct the learned model and assess its performance through the cost module. Another recent work on self-awareness architecture is based on hierarchical-agent modeling [25] to interact with the environment. The proposed architecture applies self-aware functionalities in terms of agent hierarchy. In [25], one of the essential components of self-awareness, the generative model interaction, and incremental learning ability of learned models are not considered. In MASAA, the hierarchy is based on sensor data (i.e., exteroceptive and proprioceptive data) and model aggregation to accommodate any new interaction

modalities in the explored environment. Approaches based on proprioceptive physiological signals logged from users to analyze their emotional response ([26], [27], [28]), could also be fused in this architecture to further ensure safety of the whole system.

B. Self-localization

Knowledge of the state of an autonomous agent can be obtained in two different ways. In the first way, the agent has a map of the environment but does not know its exact state in the environment. Since it does not know its initial position on the map as well, it needs to use its sensors and motion models to estimate its state. In the second way, the agent has no information about the environment, so it needs to create it by itself, using a process that enables it to learn from data. Learning the environment's latent state (hidden key features) lets an agent do filtering as an online state estimation, where its state and part of the environment are updated as new measurements become available. The smoothing technique helps the filtering process by estimating the complete trajectory from the complete set of measurements.

In autonomous driving, an agent has to localize itself and interact with other objects in the environment; hence, localization and interaction are significant steps in our scenario. Localization for automated driving has already been widely used to set up car navigation systems. Different methods, like the one in [29], were introduced to estimate a vehicle's pose. The combination of different sensors can make localization systems more robust so that it is possible for them to adapt to environmental changes, e.g., using GPS with monitoring cameras [30], GPS with smart environment sensing system [31], and GPS with visual odometry using EKF [32]. Also, in [33], GPS-based vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) communication supported by a monocular camera for localization has been studied. Rife et al. [34] have used V2V GPS communication and vision-based lane-boundary detection as a collaborative navigation. Among the methods to improve the V2V, communication-based localization [35] introduced vehicle-to-infrastructure communication between vehicles and infrastructure through magnet detection. Recently, infrastructure-based localization [36] has been proposed to counter local errors and communication interference in V2V communication. Feature-Based Monocular SLAM [16] introduced semantic segmentation to compensate for correspondences from moving objects. Jiawei et al. in [18] presented Fast Direct Stereo Visual SLAM for localization and mapping, by optimizing the scale LiDAR scan points to minimize photometric error.

Due to noisy sensors and other environmental sensitivities of GPS-based models, other models are becoming more attractive and reliable. To achieve robust vehicle localization, LiDAR based models with particle filter [37] was introduced based on A^* algorithm. Also, methods like [38] used LiDAR point cloud and IMU wheel speed data. Methods [39], [40] also introduced DL algorithms to extract location and orientation information from the point cloud data. LiDAR-based methods have better depth information for performing localization and detection, but they use expensive sensors and computationally intensive operations.

Other related works use Dynamic Bayesian networks (DBNs) for state estimation, such as distributed state estimation and detection of abnormalities [41] on lower dimensional data; predicting intentions and trajectories simultaneously for pedestrians [42] and vehicles; a semi-supervised method to model the interaction of multiple agents with DBNs [43]. Furthermore, [44], which considers lower-dimensional data, predicts matched trajectories with the observed one as an imitation learning.

To realize self-localization and interaction, fusing sensor information will not be sufficient. To explore further, a robust sensor and a model fusion which can integrate incremental learning capabilities (considering different models incrementally built from experience) are needed, and this is a crucial step forward in achieving self-localization and interaction within an environment. For this, we fuse exteroceptive and proprioceptive sensory information that fills the gap of noisy measurements, allowing us to measure deviations from learned models through a cost module. Our model gives a great importance to this cost module through the introduction of anomaly signals and incremental learning system hierarchies.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our proposed model is inspired by the proposed architecture of the general AI by Lecun [22], and by Seth's general controlled hallucination theory [19]. We consider three main modules that are closely related to our work. In his work, Lecun defined five models: perception, world, short-term memory, cost, and actor models. The perception module mainly deals with a better representation of the environment from the inside out, or as Anil Seth calls it, controlled hallucination [19]. Controlled hallucination is a perception theory explaining how things in the world, appearing in perceptual experience, are the construction of the brain. Perceptual predictions flow predominantly in a top-down direction, from the brain to the actual world (inside to outside) direction. Prediction errors flow in a bottom-up direction, from the real world to the brain (outside to inside) direction. The brain uses these prediction error signals to update its predictions. The proposed models are based on this theory to represent and estimate the future states of interacting agents. While performing these tasks, an agent needs to minimize critical costs through the short term memory model, and maintain other intrinsic non-trainable costs to keep track of its state and safely operate in the environment.

Our proposed architecture coordinates different and inter-related aspects of the agent self-aware functionalities, from the sensory stimuli to the actuation modules, as shown in Fig. 1. The sensing module is a hardware module interfacing with the external world by translating physical stimuli into an initial internal representation. It produces a time series of different observations for both the WM and MMP modules. The WM process focuses its attention on the incoming lower dimensional data (e.g., odometry), which provides more direct information on the agent's self and other agents, as time-varying units acting in a single reference framework, and produces vocabularies representing itself in a context. The

MMP module uses the WM vocabulary as a guiding attentive knowledge to represent higher-dimensional data (e.g., vision) in a context, focusing on the feature modalities that can be mapped onto WM vocabularies. The MMP module can reduce dimensionality and learn descriptions of higher dimensional data (like images or LiDAR) that can be compared and mapped to the WM representations, enriching them in a Situation model. The integrated WM representation is used as an encoded collection memory of sensorial active experiences of the agent, to be functional when the agent has to perform experienced tasks (e.g., overtaking). The learned WM Situation model is applied under a First-Person viewpoint, as a result of embedded explicit relations between external and internal variables. The resulting First-Person model is used to execute a particular task, and is compared to the current situation in the short-term memory module using an inference algorithm. The short-term memory module is the communication module, which is the interaction medium using Markov Jump Particle Filtering. When the Active First-Person module is effective, all learned vocabularies can be adjusted based on new experiences. The updating process will be carried out if the anomaly resulting from the experience is greater than a threshold. Anomalies are considered as costs under the free energy principle (evaluating what the model predicts and what the sensors are measuring) that the model aims to minimize through online and offline learning phases. The threshold is computed in the Cost module using different probabilistic distance measures. The updating process is part of the online incremental learning module and offline retraining processes. The costs are new information sources, and based on these the integrated models reprocess data. The Active First-Person module is an online process that selects actions based on learned policies, and transfers action commands to the Actuation module.

We incorporate the perception module (MMP) as experience modeling, the World Model as a combination of first-person and situation models having one or more MMPs, and the short-term memory as a core communication component of the entire architecture of our proposed system. The perception model is multi-modal [45] as it is composed of multi-sensory signals integrated to predict the situation thoroughly, from both higher dimensional and lower dimensional information. In comparison, the WM starts learning as an evolution from lower-dimensional sensors. These eventually generate cognitive knowledge as lower-dimensional vocabularies, which then train the MMP model. The third module, the short-term memory, includes critic costs, and is represented as a dynamic module composed of Markov Jump Particle Filters (MJPFs) [46], connecting all the other models. In [22], these modules are described in a more abstract and conceptual manner. On the other hand, this work builds interrelated models to progressively acquire incremental knowledge through the cost module.

Currently, our system model has three components. The first component is the one sensing the environment and itself, which gathers exteroceptive and proprioceptive sensory data. These collected data will be processed and transferred to the second and third component models (WM and MMP). The

WM processes the data and produces the vocabularies related to the lower dimensional data. These WM vocabularies will be used in the MMP component to guide the training of the higher-dimensional data using cluster-guided KVAE (see Fig. 3). MASAA can be explained in three major phases:

- 1) An unsupervised Low dimensional data learning phase
- 2) A self supervised higher dimensional data learning phase
- 3) An online state estimation (for interacting agents) phase

The first two initial phases are the building blocks of the self-awareness model, and the third phase is the testing phase of the self-aware agent modeled in the first two steps. The first stage learns (from odometry sensor data only) the state information of the ego-agent, and the interacting agent's relative state information, generating initial WM vocabularies. The second stage learns the higher-dimensional data from both sensors (image and odometry), focusing the attention on the lower-dimensional data. Hence, both WM learned HDBN vocabularies and interdependencies, guide the learning of the MMP vocabularies composed of video and odometry coupled GS-HDBNs. Stage three employs the learned Self-awareness model to allow the agent to analyze new video sequences, coming from interactive experiences, in a self-aware way.

Specifically, we modeled the interaction between two agents. One of the agents is trained to learn how to overtake the second neighboring agent and navigate to its destination. This self-aware and interaction-aware intelligence is learned from the fusion of odometry and video data. We fused odometry and video data for the following primary purposes:

- To focus the attention of learning the MMP vocabularies towards the learned modalities of the WM;
- To make the action of an agent more explainable;
- To have representations of environmental scenes that are comprehensible;
- To minimize a risk as a fail-safe mechanism in case of sensor failure.

We chose the overtaking interaction representation as an intermediate complex (with dynamic motion changes and interactions with dynamic objects) task operating in a time-varying reference system, which is challenging for data-driven methodologies.

A. World Module

Learning starts from the WM. In this model, we have lower-dimensional data that should be trained to focus the attention of the MMP model towards learning the best feature representations of the higher-dimensional data.

Low-dimensional data learning: As a first stage, the WM-MA (MA = Multi-Agent) and WM-SA (SA = Single Agent) proprioceptive learning is applied. WM-MA takes sensory observations of the odometry module that contain the positional information of the agents along axis x and y i.e., $z_{t,u_i}^o = [x_{t,u_i}, y_{t,u_i}]$. The subscript t refers to the time step, whereas u_i discriminates the i -th (u_1 : agent 1 and u_2 : agent 2) agent involved in the interaction. A Null Force Filter (NFF) [47] is employed to obtain the first order Generalized States (GSs) \tilde{z}_{t,u_i}^o , which comprise position and velocity of each agent, i.e., $\tilde{z}_{t,u_i}^o = [x_{t,u_i}, y_{t,u_i}, v_{x_{t,u_i}}, v_{y_{t,u_i}}]$. We further

(a) Multi-Agent H-DBN.

(b) Single-Agent H-DBN.

Fig. 2: The Hierarchical Dynamic Bayesian Networks are generative models composed of probabilistic links. These links describe messages, that are casual-effect inferences and can explain any decision inside the learned model. (a) The Multi-Agent H-DBN illustrates the interaction which models the inter-relation between the higher and lower dimensional vocabularies, and also represents multi-agent interaction knowledge through a relative distance vector for the overtaking interaction. (b) The single-agent H-DBN is a self-localization generative model that connects higher and lower dimensional sensory input variables, to produce a combined self-knowledge.

process the GSs to have a semantic category (cluster) depicting the movement modality of both agents using the Growing Neural Gas (GNG) algorithm [48]. An eight-dimensional feature vector \mathcal{F}_{t,u_1}^o w.r.t. u_1 , is provided as input for the clustering algorithm, and can be written as:

$$\mathcal{F}_{t,u_1}^o = [x_{t,u_1}, y_{t,u_1}, v_{x_{t,u_1}}, v_{y_{t,u_1}}, \Delta x_{t,u_{12}}, \Delta y_{t,u_{12}}, \Delta v_{x_{t,u_{12}}}, \Delta v_{y_{t,u_{12}}}], \quad (1)$$

where $\{\Delta x_{t,u_{12}}, \Delta y_{t,u_{12}}\}$ and $\{\Delta v_{x_{t,u_{12}}}, \Delta v_{y_{t,u_{12}}}\}$ are the relative positions and velocities of the interacting vehicle u_1 w.r.t. the neighbouring vehicle u_2 , which are computed as follows;

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta x_{t,u_{12}} &= x_{t,u_1} - x_{t,u_2}, \\ \Delta y_{t,u_{12}} &= y_{t,u_1} - y_{t,u_2}, \\ \Delta v_{x_{t,u_{12}}} &= v_{x_{t,u_1}} - v_{x_{t,u_2}}, \\ \Delta v_{y_{t,u_{12}}} &= v_{y_{t,u_1}} - v_{y_{t,u_2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

On the other hand, in the WM-SA, the sensory observations of the odometry module are composed of the positional information of the agent along axis x and y , as $z_t^o = [x_t, y_t]$. Here, since we wanted to model the proprioceptive information, we only need to learn the internal dynamics of the overtaking agent. Hence, as in the WM-MA, we also apply NFF to obtain the second order Generalized States (GSs) \tilde{z}_t^o , which comprises position, velocity, and acceleration. We also include other motion parameters, such as the magnitude of the velocity, and the angular velocity, to have better semantics of the WM. The GNG algorithm is then applied on these eight dimensional vectors:

$$\tilde{z}_t^o = [x_t, y_t, v_{x_t}, v_{y_t}, v_{\text{norm}_t}, a_{x_t}, a_{y_t}, \omega_t], \quad (3)$$

where v_{x_t} and v_{y_t} are first order time derivatives w.r.t. position x and position y , respectively; v_{norm_t} is the magnitude of

the velocity; a_{x_t} and a_{y_t} are second order time derivatives w.r.t. position x and position y , respectively; ω_t is the angular velocity.

Once we learn the MMP model, the modeled agent has a prior belief of the environment and its state. In the World Model, the overtaking agent should be able to localize itself, and predict the state of the neighboring agent from the observed video frame sequences. Both exteroceptive and proprioceptive information are transferred from the MMP model as experience modeling. The transport (inter-model communication) between the SM and FPM is a learned process that handles knowledge transfer between the situation and first-person models. To clarify further, an agent can learn from the interaction of two external agents without involving itself as a third person, called Situation Model knowledge. It can also learn from its actions as a First Person model when it involves itself in the interaction. The transfer of this knowledge can be learned as a transportation process. Through the imitation learning process, the knowledge gained from situation models, can be utilized to solve related tasks when used in the first-person models. The more related the tasks, the easier it is to transfer or cross-utilize the acquired knowledge. In this case, we want to transfer the learned knowledge of different but interrelated aspects of the environment, modeled as first-person and situation models to share the knowledge between them.

B. Multi-Modal Perception Module

In this section we discuss how the Multi-Modal Perception (MMP) module represents the environment we model inside the artificial agent through the integrated sensors to better understand the system. This module combines self-awareness and situational sensory fusion modality representations. Self-awareness allows an agent to monitor and predict its state

at each step; simultaneously, the situational modality observes the environment for smooth interaction with other agents in the shared environment. In Fig. (2b) single-agent and (2a) multi-agent perception modules are represented in multi-sensory generalized H-DBN frameworks. The SA-HDBN determines the self-state evolution corresponding to the environment (self-awareness) and, at the same time, the MA-HDBN regulates the contextual understanding of the environment using the self-state evolution where the agent operates.

Higher-dimensional data learning: We have two cluster-based dynamic Variational Autoencoders named MMP-MA and MMP-SA dynamic-VAEs. Both networks are utilized to reduce the video data’s dimensionality, and to learn a representation of the latent state for later reconstruction and inference. MMP-MA learns the interaction model between the two agents, giving us exteroceptive information in the World Model. MMP-SA generates the proprioceptive information of the ego agent in the World Model. This type of architecture makes our model a hybrid between end-to-end and modular learning approaches.

After learning from the odometry modality, we use the learned vocabulary to train the video models. For this purpose, a Kalman Variational Autoencoder (KVAE) [49] is employed to obtain the latent states $a_t^{(u_i)v}$ corresponding to the video of the training data $x_t^{(u_i)v}$. To elaborate more, we have two hidden states, i.e., $a_t^{(u_i)v}$ and $z_t^{(u_i)v}$, which represent the content of an image and its corresponding dynamics, respectively. In the VAE encoding phase, we encode $\{A_k\}_{k=1,\dots,K}$ and $\{C_k\}_{k=1,\dots,K}$ matrices that are a set of K globally learned basic transition and pseudo-observation models, respectively. While training, since our main objective is to localize both agents only from the video sequence at each time instant, we learned two additional pseudo observation models, i.e., D and E , from the latent distribution and the odometry vocabulary. These matrices encode the information of the location parameters of interacting agents; therefore, we used four matrices (A , C , D , and E) representing our complex model.

The VAE encoder, for both MMP-SA and MMP-MA settings, is a three-layer convolutional neural network with 32, 64, 128 units in each layer, kernel size of 3x3, stride of 2, and LeakyReLU activation function. The decoder is an equally sized network for deconvolution. As an optimizer, we use ADAM with an initial learning rate of 0.001, and an exponential decay scheme with a rate of 0.97 every 20 epochs.

For improved reconstruction and easier inference of objectives, for the single agent we set the minimum motion related latent state $z_t^v \in \mathbb{R}^4$ and content related latent state $a_t^v \in \mathbb{R}^{10}$. In the multi-agent setting, $z_t^{(u_i)v} \in \mathbb{R}^8$ and $a_t^{(u_i)v}$ is the same dimension as the single agent $a_t^{(u_i)v} \in \mathbb{R}^{10}$. Motion related latent states are matched with the parameters of the odometry generalized state vectors $z_t^o \in \mathbb{R}^4$ for the single agent, and $z_t^{(u_i)o} \in \mathbb{R}^8$ for multi-agent. The pseudo-observation matrix dimensions are $D_t \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times M \times L}$ and $E_t \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times L}$, where N is number of clusters, M is the dimension of the cluster mean vector, and L is the dimension of the motion related latent state vector of the video data.

The trained odometry vocabulary $\tilde{s}_k^{(u_i)o}$ is employed to guide the model to assign a semantic category to the latent states. The two latent states are modeled as follows:

$$a_{t,u_i} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k} \times C_{k,u_i} \times z_{t,u_i} + v_{t,u_i}, \quad (4)$$

where a_{t,u_i} is the content distribution that is obtained from the dynamical latent state z_{t,u_i} through a pseudo-observation model. On the other hand, z_{t,u_i} at consequent time instants are connected through the following dynamical model:

$$z_{t+1,u_i} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k} \times A_{k,u_i} \times z_{t,u_i} + \omega_{t,u_i} \quad (5)$$

In Eq. 4 and in Eq. 5, v_t and ω_t are Gaussian noises; matrices $\{C_{k,u_i}\}_{k=1\dots K}$ and $\{A_{k,u_i}\}_{k=1\dots K}$ represent a set of pseudo-observation models and transition models, respectively, as defined in the traditional Kalman Filter (KF) [50]. These models are combined through a probabilistic vector $\alpha_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k}$ as a *guiding vector*, which guides the model to assign a semantic category (cluster) to the dynamic video state z_{t,u_i} . Mathematically, $\alpha_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k}$ can be defined as follows:

$$1/\alpha_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k} = \left(d_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k}\right)^n \times \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{1}{\left(d_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k}\right)^n}, \quad (6)$$

where $d_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k} = \mathcal{D}_M((z_{t,u_i}^v), (M^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}, Q^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}))$ is the Mahalanobis distance (\mathcal{D}_M) [51] calculated between each latent state distribution z_{t,u_i}^v and the probability distribution of each cluster of the odometry module ($M^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}, Q^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}$). $M^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}$ is the mean of cluster \tilde{s}_k , and $Q^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}$ is its covariance, i.e., the probability distribution is a Gaussian. In the first iteration, z_{t,u_i}^v will be assigned to the superstates corresponding to the shortest distance $d_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k}$ values. After the first iteration, $d_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k}$ will be multiplied by the previous $\alpha_{t,u_i}^{\tilde{s}_k}$ value to cluster the z_{t,u_i}^v , having similar probability distributions. n is a temperature value used to assign, to image sequences, the highest probability of the WM cluster.

In [49], after performing Kalman smoothing, four main losses are used to optimize the model:

- the traditional reconstruction loss (between $x_t^{(u_i)v}$ and its VAE reconstruction $\hat{x}_t^{(u_i)v}$).
- the KullbackLeibler Divergence term of the VAE, which represent the VAE loss \mathcal{L}_{VAE} ;
- a transition loss \mathcal{L}_{trans} enforcing the learning of the transition models A and B.
- an emission loss \mathcal{L}_{emiss} enforcing the learning of the emission models C.

In our implementation, as transition loss, we used the Bhattacharya distance DB between the smoothed latent state at time $t+1$, i.e., $z_{s_{t+1}}$, and the state predicted from z_{s_t} using the matrices A:

$$\mathcal{L}_{trans} = D_B(z_{s_{t+1}}, Az_{s_t}) \quad (7)$$

For the emission loss, we used DB between the latent state a_t and its dynamics predicted from z_{s_t} using the matrices C:

$$\mathcal{L}_{emiss} = D_B(a_t, Cz_{s_t}) \quad (8)$$

Fig. 3: MASAA: Self-representation learning and inference frameworks. A learned vocabulary of proprioceptive information (controlled hallucination) drives exteroceptive information learning.

While training, we also learned the *zero-th order observation matrices* $\hat{z}_{t,u_1}^o, \hat{z}_{t,u_2}^o$ as follows:

$$\hat{z}_{t,u_1}^o = D^{\tilde{s}_k} \times z_{t,u_1}^o + E^{\tilde{s}_k} + M^{\tilde{s}_k} + e_{1t}, \quad (9)$$

$$\hat{z}_{t,u_2}^o = z_{t,u_1}^o + r_{d_t, u_{12}} + e_{2t}, \quad (10)$$

where the prediction of \hat{z}_{t,u_1}^o and \hat{z}_{t,u_2}^o are performed by minimizing the errors (e_{1t}, e_{2t}) w.r.t. the ground truth odometry. $r_{d_t, u_{12}}$ is a relative distance vector, which can be mathematically defined as:

$$r_{d_t, u_{12}} = [\Delta x_{t, u_{12}}, \Delta y_{t, u_{12}}, \Delta v_{x_{t, u_{12}}}, \Delta v_{y_{t, u_{12}}}], \quad (11)$$

Optimization is performed through cross modality losses using *Huber Loss functions* [52].

During the (online) testing phase, the learned vocabularies $s_{k, u_1}^v, \tilde{s}_{k, u_1}^o$ and $\hat{z}_{t, u_1}^o, \hat{z}_{t, u_2}^o$ are employed to predict the trajectories of the interacting agents.

One thing to note in the MMP module is that the mathematical notations are presented by assuming multi-agent interactions. When a single agent is trained, the mathematical models will be updated. The pseudo-observation model becomes:

$$a_t = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_t^{\tilde{s}_k} \times C_k \times z_t + v_t$$

The dynamical model connects z_t values at consequent times:

$$z_{t+1} = \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_t^{\tilde{s}_k} \times A_k \times z_t + \omega_t$$

As a result, we have two sets of vocabularies from both odometry and video modalities as follows,

Odometry Vocabularies: Cluster mean ($M^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}$), cluster covariance ($Q^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}$), transition probability (T) and time spent in each cluster ($T^{(g)}$).

Video Vocabularies: Cluster mean ($M^{(s_k, a_t)^v}, M^{(s_k, z_t)^v}$) and cluster covariance ($Q^{(s_k, a_t)^v}, Q^{(s_k, z_t)^v}$).

C. MMP and WM Interaction

These two models (MMP and WM) should communicate robustly in the online operation (testing phase). The main task of these modules is to fuse models and sensors to determine the state of the ego-vehicle and the interacting agent. Since we do not have the exact state information (position and velocity) for both agents, except the learned models of the interacting agent, what is recommended in the literature is to use Interacting Multiple Model (IMM) filters [53]. So, we are fusing multiple models with many hypotheses and combining them based on their strength (low error) to get better overall estimations. Learning well-structured models should provide optimal results in estimating ego-state and interacting agent states. We may face a challenge in that, even if updating the process in estimation is easier. Predicting other neighboring agents is hard because we do not have control over their movement intentions. When predicting motion, we have to consider the following main issues:

- 1) The dynamics and kinematics of the system;
- 2) The commands and known inputs;

3) The unknown and random inputs.

Hence, we have to consider these situations when estimating any future state of any moving agent, including ego-motion. The integrated filter has to access the dynamics as a form of a mathematical model. If we are considering ego-motion, the filter will have access to the control inputs directly. Regarding the unknowns affecting the model accuracy, the filter should account for the process noise. If this noise is very high, the certainty of the prediction will drop.

Regarding the interacting agent, since we are modeling uncooperative agents, we do not have the access to the control inputs directly, so the filter should consider it as unknown in prediction. Introducing more unknowns to our models makes the prediction less confident, leading us to increase the process noise. This implies that we have to trust more the correction measurement. Since sensors are very noisy, if the process noise is very high, the difference between the actual situation and the estimation will be very high. Therefore, integrated multiple (multi-hypothesis) filter models should be applied simultaneously, with different prediction and process noise models. By fusing the output of each filter based on the model likelihood or averaging them, we can have a better estimate.

In our model, the communication mechanism is mainly in the short-term memory, comprised of Multi-Agent Combined Markov Jump Particle Filters (MAC-MJPFs). We chose these filters because they are integrated and well-suited to adjust particle estimations, by fast re-initialization, when the agent changes its motion. As a single integrated multi-filter, it allows updating each filter after each measurement to get an updated state and state covariance based on the fusion of the most likely models based on their weights. Our algorithm MAC-MJPFs is composed of interrelated MJPFs which have to handle:

- Video latent state prediction;
- Generalized proprioceptive state prediction;
- Interacting agent generalized state prediction.

The *Multi-Agent Coupled Markov Jump Particle Filter* (MAC-MJPF) is proposed for the prediction of the trajectories $(\tilde{z}_{t,u_1}^o, \tilde{z}_{t,u_2}^o)$ at the online phase. MAC-MJPF employs KF and PF to make inferences about the future states over the proposed H-DBN model. The MAC-MJPF algorithm is detailed in Alg. 1, and represented with a flow chart in Fig. 4(e) (for details also refer to [3]).

IV. DATASET

Two semi-autonomous real vehicles, called *iCab1* and *iCab2* [55], are employed to perform the overtaking experiments. Since our objective is the localization of the interacting agents, we considered an overtaking maneuver in which *iCab2* overtakes *iCab1*. *iCab1* and *iCab2* are u_1 and u_2 in the previous notations. We display the lower dimensional odometry trajectories from the overtaking experiments in Fig. 4c, and the grayscale video images in Fig. 4a.

In addition to the above dataset, we tested our model on data coming from the well-known CARLA simulator [56], built from the ground to support the development, training, and validation of autonomous driving systems. We considered an overtaking scenario to make it coherent with our proposed

Algorithm 1: Localization and Interaction algorithm.

```

1 Input:  $M^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}, Q^{(\tilde{s}_k)^o}, T, T^{(g)}, M^{(s_k, a_t)^v}, M^{(s_k, z_t)^v};$ 
2  $Q^{(s_k, a_t)^v}, Q^{(s_k, z_t)^v}, x_t^{(u_1)^v}$ 
3 for  $t = 1, \dots, \tau \leftarrow$  Time evolution do
4   Obtain image latent state using VAE:  $a_t^{(u_1)^v}, \sigma_t^{(u_1)^v}$  and
5   Obtain latent state covariance  $\leftarrow \Sigma_t^{(u_1)^v} \sim I_L \times \sigma_t^{(u_1)^v}$ 
6   where  $L$  is the number of latent state features
7   Compute distances of video encodings from video clusters:
8    $d_t^{(u_1)^v} = \mathcal{D}_B((a_t^{(u_1)^v}, \Sigma_t^{(u_1)^v}), (M^{(s_k, a_t)^v}, Q^{(s_k, a_t)^v}))$ ,
   where  $s = 1, \dots, K$ 
9   Calculate probabilistic guiding vector  $\alpha_t^{(\tilde{s}_k^{u_1})}$  using Eq. 6
10 Begin Filtering
11 for  $n = 1, \dots, N \leftarrow$  number of Particles do
12   if  $t == 1$  then
13      $W_n = \frac{1}{N} \leftarrow$  weight of the particles
14     Initialize the video and odometry vocabularies:
15      $s_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^v} \sim p(z_t^{(u_1)^v} | s_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^v})$ 
16      $\tilde{s}_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^o} \sim p(\tilde{z}_t^{(u_1)^o} | \tilde{s}_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^o})$ 
17   else
18     UPDATE:
19     Update video states:
20      $z_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^v}, \Sigma_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^v} =$ 
21      $KF_{update}^{Video}(z_{t|t-1,n}^{(u_1)^v}, \Sigma_{t|t-1,n}^{(u_1)^v}, C_{t,n}^{s_{t|t,n}^{u_1}}, a_{t,n}^{(u_1)^v}, \Sigma_{t,n}^{(u_1)^v})$ 
22     Update  $\tilde{z}_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^o}$  (itself) according to Eq.(9)
23     Update  $\tilde{z}_{t|t,n}^{(u_2)^o}$  according to Eq.(10)
24     Re-sample if  $\sum_n \frac{1}{W_n^2} <$  threshold [54]
25   end if
26   PREDICTION:
27   Predict vocabulary of video:
28    $s_{t+1,n}^{(u_1)^v} \sim T(\tilde{s}_{t,n}^o)$ ,
29   Predict vocabulary of odometry:
30    $\tilde{s}_{t+1,n}^{(u_1)^o} \sim T(\tilde{s}_{t,n}^o)$ ,
31   Predict Video latent state:
32    $z_{t+1|t,n}^{(u_1)^v}, \Sigma_{t+1|t,n}^{(u_1)^v} = KF_{pred}^{Video}(z_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^v}, \Sigma_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^v})$ 
33   Predict location of  $u_1$  (itself) and  $r_{d_t}^{u_12}$  wrt interacting agent  $u_2$  :
34    $\tilde{z}_{t+1|t,n}^{(u_1)^o}, \Sigma_{t+1|t,n}^{(u_1)^o}, r_{d_t}^{u_12} = KF_{pred}^{Odometry}(z_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^v}, \Sigma_{t|t,n}^{(u_1)^v})$ 
35   Predict location of neighboring agent  $u_2$  using  $r_{d_t}^{u_12}$ :
36    $\tilde{z}_{t+1|t,n}^{(u_2)^o}, \Sigma_{t+1|t,n}^{(u_2)^o} = \tilde{z}_{t+1|t,n}^{(u_1)^o}, \Sigma_{t+1|t,n}^{(u_1)^o} + r_{d_t}^{u_12}$ 
37   Smoothing:  $\tilde{z}_{t|t-1}^{(u_1)^o} = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{z}_{t|t-1}^{(u_1)^o}]_n$  and  $\tilde{z}_{t|t-1}^{(u_2)^o} = \mathbb{E}[\tilde{z}_{t|t-1}^{(u_2)^o}]_n$ 
38   end for
39   Output: Predicted trajectories  $\tilde{z}_{t|t-1}^{(u_1)^o}$  (oneself) and the interacting agent
    $\tilde{z}_{t|t-1}^{(u_2)^o}$ .
40 end for

```

method. Both datasets are pre-processed to synchronize video and odometry data, and also synchronize the agents. Fig. 4 (a) shows image sequences that are the last part of the overtaking operation, which are named cluster number 8 for iCab1 and cluster number 6 for iCab2 respectively, in the odometry plot of Fig. 4 (c). Fig. 4 (b) shows sample image sequences around the start of the overtaking operation, which are named cluster 7 for Agent1 and cluster 5 for Agent2 respectively, in the odometry plot of Fig. 4 (d).

To test the generalizability of our model, we also used a public dataset (KITTI [57]). We specifically tested the single agent localization using these six sequences (sequence: 00, 01, 02, 03, 04, and 05), and compared our results with the state-of-the-art methods.

V. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We performed eight experiments using the CARLA simulator [56]. Training includes four overtaking experiments (Exp:01, Exp:02, Exp:03, and Exp:04) performed in normal daylight conditions. Validation comprises two experiments

Fig. 4: Training dataset: (a) Interacting and overtaking vehicle’s video information from real iCab data set [55]. (b) Interacting and overtaking vehicle’s video information from CARLA [56] simulator data set. (c) and (d) are clustered positional trajectories of the interacting and overtaking vehicles of iCab and CARLA data sets, respectively. Arrows indicate the direction of motion of vehicles encoded in \tilde{s}_{k,u_i} and different colors represent the different clusters. (e) Flow chart model of multi-modal MJPF: a detailed description, including stages of the filtering process, are described in algorithm 1.

(a) Training trajectory: overtaking interaction takes place in a starting point of a curved zone. (b) Training trajectory: overtaking interaction takes place in a curved area.

(c) Testing trajectory: Overtaking is performed in straight area under the condition of heavy rain. (d) Testing trajectory. This scenario is performed to test traffic light anomaly and light rain in the evening time of the day.

Fig. 5: (a) As encircled by the blue oval shape the overtaking interaction is performed after both agents change lane. (b) This experiment resembles the curved regions of the World Model. (c) The overtaking is performed in a different region from the training. (d) The interacting agents will stop until the traffic light turns red.

(Exp:05 and Exp:07). Exp:05 is performed under normal daytime environmental conditions, as in the training cases. Exp:07 is performed at sunset time. The remaining experiments (Exp:06 and Exp:08), shown in Fig. 5c and 5d, are used for testing. Exp:06 is performed in light rain conditions in the evening (sunset), with a stop maneuver due to a red traffic light. Exp:08 is performed in heavy rain conditions while performing the overtaking task, which is different from the learned overtaking one.

In the iCab dataset, training includes three overtaking experiments (Exp:01, Exp:02, and Exp:03); the validation experiment is Exp:04, while Exp:05 is the testing experiment.

In addition to these experiments, we considered following (an agent follows instead of overtaking) experiments. These experiments are performed to analyze the behaviours of different models (following and overtaking) tested on the same scenario: first, testing the overtaking scenario on the wrong training model, which is the following model, and then with the appropriate model, the overtaking model. These will give us the extent to which our model can generalize a given scenario.

All these experiments are analyzed to better represent the self-state of an agent and the base interaction with the environment. In MASAA, however, other interaction types (e.g., an interaction with an unmanned aerial vehicle that can be analyzed to jointly predict trajectories while performing a particular task) with similar configurations can also be performed.

VI. LEARNED H-DBN MODELS

The agent is able to learn H-DBNs, representing the learned vocabularies of self-localization and interaction, that will be used for Bayesian inference. Combined vocabularies, representing the WM and MMP, are learned for multi-agent and single-agent networks as shown in Fig. 2a and 2b, respectively.

A. World Model Network

WM network is a low-dimensional cluster network used to steer the MMP model towards the best features representing the WM vocabularies. It is a low-dimensional generative model representing how an agent, as a point in a 2D space, interacts with the environment when doing a particular task (e.g., overtaking), as shown in Fig. 4 (c, d). It is the base knowledge (Fig. 3 phase 1) guiding the higher dimensional knowledge learning process (Fig. 3 phase 2).

B. Multi-Agent CG-KVAE Network

In the MMP, we have two distinct and related networks. The first network is the Multi-agent MMP which is responsible for learning interactions based on the relative state estimation. It is a generative model of higher dimensional data (e.g., video) guided by the WM model vocabularies. For example, in the case of overtaking, the MMP module learned the motion predictions coherent with changes in the video content. This multimodal coupling between learned models represents a basic feature of a self-aware agent. It has two interrelated sub-networks, each one handling each interacting agent trained together. These sub-networks allow us to model the state of one agent in terms of the other agent's state.

C. Single-Agent CG-KVAE Network

Instead of learning the relative state of an agent, here the model has learned to predict the ego-motion parameters, which are the generalized states from the higher dimensional sensory input. The cognitive knowledge of an agent's self-state will allow the agent to interact with the environment and execute any possible maneuvering tasks.

VII. RESULTS

As a result of applying the trained models within the MASAA architecture, the derived features are used to predict the state of an agent and its neighboring agent. More specifically, these features are the outputs of the SA-MMP and MA-MMP models, which will be used to predict and then act online. The differences between these trained generative predictive models and the current situations are evaluated within the Cost module, by using anomaly signals obtained according to the free energy minimization principle.

Training and testing were carried out on an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3070 GPU laptop with 8GB GPU memory.

Table I shows how the WM guides the MMP to learn the best features related to generalized states; Table II displays the analysis of time, RMSE drift, and number of particle of MAC-MJPF; Tables III and IV show inference errors related to different datasets and models. Table IV is shown in Section

Fig. 6: Sample learned trajectories. (a) WM based learned trajectory, from MMP of a multi-agent trajectory using iCab dataset. (b) WM based learned trajectory from MMP of a multi-agent trajectory, using Carla dataset. (c) WM based learned trajectory from MMP of a single-agent trajectory, using Kitti dataset.

Fig. 7: Transition probability Matrices. These probability matrices are used to govern the learning of higher dimensional data, i.e., to assign the most probable WM states to each video sequence.

IX (Supplementary Material). Anomaly signals, indicating the performance of the learned models, are shown in Fig. 8.

The results show that the proposed model has gained knowledge of self-localization and interaction, as shown in Fig. 9. The Cost module uses different anomaly signal measurement models, in different hierarchical levels, to explain the results of our model. Video content anomaly and latent state anomaly are both indicators of the MMP module, while odometry anomaly is the indicator of the WM module. KLDA indicates the integrated WM and MMP anomaly signal. Further details about these indicators are provided shortly.

TABLE I: Table displaying the temperature values according to Eq. 6, and the corresponding RMSE error between the ground truth generalized states and the learned generalized states. The RMSE values shown here are the mean of the generalized state RMSE errors. From this, the best temperature value is between 10 and 25. Hence, $n = 15$ is used in our learning models.

RMSE	$n = 5$	$n = 10$	$n = 15$	$n = 25$	$n = 50$	$n = 100$
iCab	0.0319	0.0257	0.0244	0.0274	0.0275	0.0294
Carla	0.0095	0.0093	0.0094	0.0098	0.0105	0.0110
Kitti	0.0019	0.0029	0.0036	0.0044	0.0046	0.0047

KLDA: it is an energy-based model measuring anomalies (differences between probability distributions) from the

predictive ($\pi(s_t)$) and diagnostic ($\lambda(s_{t+1})$) messages, when estimating superstates (clusters)(for details refer to [58], [59]).

$$SuperStateLevelAnomaly = KLDA(\pi(\tilde{s}_t), \lambda(\tilde{s}_{t+1}))$$

Video content anomaly: it is estimated by taking the mean square error between the latent state prediction related to the content of each image from the models ($a_{t,t-1,n}$) and the encoded latent state of the testing image ($\hat{a}_{t|t-1,n}$).

$$a_{anomaly} = \frac{1}{N} \sum (a_{t|t-1,n} - \hat{a}_{t|t-1,n})$$

Latent state anomaly: mean square error between the predicted ($z_{t,t-1,n}$) and updated state of latent state ($\hat{z}_{t|t-1,n}$). It allows us to estimate the anomaly signal related to the motion parameter corresponding to each image in sequence.

$$z_{anomaly} = \frac{1}{N} \sum (z_{t|t-1,n} - \hat{z}_{t|t-1,n})$$

Image reconstruction anomaly: the mean square error between the real image (x_t) and the reconstructed image of VAE (\hat{x}_t).

$$ImageReconstructionError = MSE(x_t, \hat{x}_t)$$

Odometry prediction anomaly: it is computed by taking the mean square error between the pseudo-observation odometry parameter ($z_{t,n}^o$) and its prediction parameter ($\hat{z}_{t,n}^o$).

$$z_{anomaly}^o = \frac{1}{N} \sum (z_{t,n}^o - \hat{z}_{t,n}^o)^2$$

The general free energy minimization concept applied at different representation levels allows the Cost module to compute and explain the behavior of anomaly signals. The anomaly signals depicted in Fig. 8 exhibit an increase in amplitude when the model encounters an interaction area it has not seen before (the learned overtaking zone is different from the testing one). Particularly, in Fig. 8b, the peaks in the anomaly signal are highlighted; the labels in the red circles represent the cause of the peak. Zone 1 is a tunnel; zone 2 is a curved area; zone 3 is the overtaking area, and zone 4 is a traffic light area. Fig. 8a, on the other hand, shows the measured anomaly signals under heavy rain conditions. The video reconstruction anomaly signal corresponding to the end of the anomaly signal is lower in amplitude in experiment 06 (Exp:06) than experiment 08 (Exp:08). This happens because Exp:08 considers a red traffic light anomaly signal, which is not present in Exp:06. These multilevel anomaly signals can be used as a basic information source to any reward-based [60] or preferred observation-based [61] learning frameworks that can be incorporated to learn from self-action in an incremental learning process.

The proposed method implemented in the MASAA architecture, not only provides an explainable cognitive framework, but can achieve good estimation performance. To demonstrate this estimation capacity, under the MAC-MJPF algorithm, Fig. 9 shows particle approximations. The particle approximations shown in Fig. 9b are more accurate than the ones reported in Fig. 9a, as both the training experiment and the testing interaction in Fig. 9b were performed in the same area. More details on errors related to the state estimation of interacting agents

TABLE II: MAC-MJPF Complexity Analysis. MAC-MJPF performs best between 50 and 500 particles, with low mean RMSE of generalized states and within acceptable time. Time is in minutes.

Number of Particles		10	50	100	500	1000	
Data Sets	iCab 420 Frames	Time	0.44	1.38	2.23	10.49	20.45
		RMSE	15.32	7.75	6.16	3.50	3.00
	Carla 180 Frames	Time	0.14	0.49	0.85	3.84	8.53
		RMSE	19.64	4.11	2.54	0.97	0.93
	Carla 160 Frames	Time	0.13	0.40	0.81	3.72	7.03
		RMSE	11.77	9.54	3.50	1.06	0.95
	Kitti 2761 Frames	Time	4.61	10.46	26.98	83.47	162.18
		RMSE	16.67	0.61	0.41	0.34	0.32
	Kitti 4541 Frames	Time	7.54	18.65	45.84	145.26	279.78
		RMSE	26.13	2.76	1.30	0.75	0.53

as a Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) drift are presented in TABLE III.

TABLE III: Table displays the quantitative analysis of the overtaking model and following model, tested with overtaking data set, based on Mean Square Error (MSE) measurement. We used the generalized training data as ground truth to compute the errors (shown in Fig. 4b).

RMSE	x	y	v_x	v_y	Experiment No.
Overtaking a1	1.7814	1.7560	0.8693	0.9646	06
Overtaking a1	1.5367	4.1848	0.8758	0.8644	08
Overtaking a2	1.7550	3.1502	0.0052	0.0049	06
Overtaking a2	1.7218	1.0127	0.0058	0.0184	08
Overtaking iCab1	0.9977	2.1985	0.0431	0.0363	05
Overtaking iCab2	1.8494	2.6795	0.0808	0.0981	05
Follow a1	24.9720	31.3412	2.0269	1.2849	09
Follow a2	61.6416	22.7203	3.6588	1.2832	09

The complexity analysis in Table II is performed with short, medium, and long sequences of testing datasets to show the MAC-MJPF performance in different covered distances.

A. Comparisons with state-of-the-art methods

The estimation results presented above demonstrate the capability of the MASAA architecture to learn and use a generative model representation for task-based systems on multimodal data (video and odometry in our case). SLAM methods are the reference class of approaches suitable for fair comparisons. Specifically, deep learning-based SLAM methods [62], [63] are being studied to generate high-level semantics and build an agent’s knowledge base to enhance the agent’s perception and intelligence. One of the goals of this paper is to evaluate how well the integrated WM, MMP, and Cost modules can work in the MASAA architecture to learn from data in an explainable representation. Hence, we compared the drift of state estimation errors in the agent state with some selected SLAM methods.

DSV-SLAM [18] is a LiDAR descriptor-based SLAM approach proposed to facilitate an efficient detection of loop closures for localization and mapping. The authors used the KITTI dataset and achieved an RMSE of 3.693% on average. Other methods like UnDeepVO [64] perform pose estimation by training deep neural networks in an unsupervised manner,

and attain an average of 4.07% RMSE drift. Li et al. [65] proposed a self-supervised learning framework to represent frame-to-frame correspondence, for depth and pose estimation, with RMSE drift of around 5%. These comparisons show that our method allows us to estimate the trajectories of interacting agents with lower RMSE drifts of 2.897%.

B. Discussion

The World Model (WM) learning process is depicted in Fig. 4 (c, d), corresponding to the iCab and CARLA multi-agent vocabularies, respectively. As shown in the plots, the number of clusters are labeled with different colors, the mean of each cluster positions with black filled circles, and cluster velocities with red arrows (phase 1 of MASAA, see Fig. 3). The movement between clusters is ruled by a transition matrix containing the transition probabilities as shown in Fig. 7. These vocabularies are the output of the world model, that are then used to train the MMP model (phase 2 of MASAA).

The attention (guiding) vector in Eq. 6, that governs the higher dimensional learning is a scaled version of the transition probability (see also Fig. 7), to assign the most probable WM states.

The results of the MMP module, shown in Fig. 6, represent the best-learned dynamic coupling between attention focusing from the WM model, and experience modeling from the MMP model. This allows the model to achieve the lowest RMSE error between the ground truth generalized states and the learned generalized states (see Table I).

These generated WM and MMP vocabularies, integrated through algorithm 1 (MAC-MJPF), corresponding to phase 3 of MASAA, are lower dimensional vocabularies (note that the output of the MMP model is also lower dimensional due to the VAE representation). This coupled knowledge is used to test the system in different environmental conditions (e.g., unseen heavy rain conditions) and in different overtaking regions (e.g., regions different from the learned overtaking regions). It also performs well as shown in Fig. 9 and Table III.

Anomaly detection is a crucial step to guarantee a closed-loop incremental learning process. The results in Fig. 8 show the capability of detecting anomalous signals that force the agent to correct its decisions. In the online testing phase, if there is an unexpected behavior and the predicted distributions are shifted compared to the learned model ones, the Active FP Model of the MASAA framework will be activated to correct these bad actions. Furthermore, by applying thresholds on each anomaly signal, the agent can use a retraining module when it faces a completely new environment.

MASAA exhibits a distinctive characteristic in learning knowledge that represents dynamic and static interaction models, as demonstrated in the coupled systems. The incremental nature (behavior) of MASAA makes it possible to build fault-tolerant systems in autonomous driving scenarios when decisions like overtaking need to be made.

C. Further Discussion on MASAA

In this paper, we have considered a particular overtaking task using our MASAA architecture. We show how MMP

(a) Anomaly signals: Exp:06

(b) Anomaly signals: Exp:08

Fig. 8: Anomaly signals for experiment six: (a) and experiment eight: (b). The color code for both experiments: pink-colored is KLDA between the predictive and diagnostic messages. The cyan-colored signal is the min likelihood of particles in each cluster. The red-colored signal is the frame reconstruction error.

(a) Testing result: Exp:06

(b) Testing result: Exp:08

Fig. 9: (a): Predictions of the trajectories corresponding to all particles. (b): Predictions of the trajectories corresponding to all particles.

and WM models can be applied to make an agent self-aware in performing experienced (learned) tasks. The models cooperate, within the learning phase, to allow the self-aware agent to store a multi-modal autobiographic memory. This can guide the agent to face new experiences by extracting the preferred observations from higher dimensional data that refine localization and anomaly detection for different interaction tasks. The remaining module, the Active FP Model, which is related to learning from action, is a component that can be integrated easily in our case study (Overtaking), as done for lower dimensional data learning and inference framework in [2].

MASAA can be easily adapted for use in various applications and different research areas, such as wireless communications, where its characteristics could be exploited to detect abnormal activities within the spectrum induced by jammers [58].

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper proposed a data-driven approach for the localization of interacting agents, based on multi-sensorial data. These data are used in a novel cognitive architecture where

all modules learn a hierarchy of inference and representation. During offline training, the vocabulary of the low-dimensional modality is used to learn the latent states and their dynamics for the video modality, thus obtaining the corresponding vocabulary. During online testing, the trajectories of the interacting agents are predicted only from the video sensory signals and the learned vocabulary. Our experiments showed that this knowledge allows an agent to localize itself, and to predict the GSs, i.e., position and velocity, of the neighboring agent from the videos in a self-supervised way. For future work, the proposed interaction model can be extended for the localization and interactions of heterogeneous agents. Learning from action will also be integrated in our novel cognitive architecture.

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